

Research Article

Polyherbal Formulation of Anti-acne Cream

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ABSTRACT

Inflammatory and non-inflammatory lesions are hallmarks of the acne disease. Acne lesions are the result of a complex pathogenesis that involves hormonal, bacterial, and immunological factors. The current study focuses on developing and assessing a herbal cream to combat this acne vulgaris etiologic agent. Dermatologists treat acne vulgaris the most frequently. The development of open and closed comedones, papules, pustules, nodules and cysts are the hallmarks of acne, a disease of the pilosebaceous unit. The aim of the research was to evaluate the safety and effectiveness of a polyherbal formulation in treating vulgaris acne in contrast to benzoyl peroxide.

INTRODUCTION

There are both inflammatory and non-inflammatory lesions associated with this disease. Eighty percent of young people worldwide suffer from acne, which has a major negative influence on their quality of life. For both sexes, the age range of 21–25 years was where frequency peaked. Due to the disease's prevalence, 20% of all dermatologist visits are related to acne.^[1] The most prevalent dermatological condition affecting pilosebaceous units is acne vulgaris. Topical therapy containing antimicrobials, comedolytics, and anti-inflammatory agents is advised for the treatment of acne.^[2] Long-term inflammation of the pilosebaceous units caused by acne vulgaris is typified by seborrhea, comedones, erythematous

papules, and pustules; less commonly, nodules, deep pustules or pseudocysts appear, is sometimes coupled with scarring.^[3,4] Four etiological factors are linked to the pathophysiology of acne: elevated sebum production, aberrant keratinization of the pilosebaceous duct, Propionibacterium acnes colonisation of the follicular microflora, and the body's inflammatory and immune response. The main microbe present in the sebaceous gland is Propionibacterium acnes. Its capacity to form and persist as a biofilm within the pilosebaceous unit may be linked to its role in the pathogenesis of acne.^[5,6]

Plant Profile

1] Harad

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Fig 1: Harad

Common name: Harad, Haritaki.

Synonym: Abhaya, amruta.

Scientific name: Terminalia chebula.

Family: Combretaceae.

Biological source: Terminalia chebula Retz.

Chemical constituents: phenolic acids, benzoic acids, cinnamic acids, flavonoids, beta-sitosterol (a plant sterol used to reduce cholesterol levels) and glycosides.

Applications: Anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antimicrobial.

Taxonomical Classification:

Kingdome	Plantae
Subkingdom	Angiosperms
Class	Monocotyledons
Subclass	Epigynae
Division	Magnoliopsida
Order	Myrtales
Family	Combretaceae
Genus	Terminalia
Species	Chebula

Pharmacological Properties:

1. Antifungal activity

Aqueous extract of T. chebula show antifungal activity against a number of dermatophytes (e.g. Epidermophyton, Floccosum, Microsporum gypseum and Tricophyton rubrum) and yeasts (e.g. Candida albicans). Aqueous, alcoholic and ethyl acetate extracts of leaves of Haritaki was also tested against five pathogenic fungi (Aspergillus flavus, A. niger, Alternaria brassicicola, A. alternate and Helminthosporium tetramera) with the help of paper disc method.

2. Anti-carcinogenic activity

Harad fruit extract may have the potential the growth or increase in the number of cancer cells and induced death in several types of cancer cells, including human breast cancer cells, human bone cancer cells, and prostate cancer cells in lab-scale studies.⁷ Acetone extract of T. chebula has been reported to contain Phytochemicals with promising antimutagenic and ant carcinogenic properties.⁸

3. Antibacterial activity

Antibacterial activity of T. chebula exhibited against various Gram positive and negative bacteria such as Salmonella typhi, Staphylococcus epidermidis, Staphylococcus aureus, iBacillus subtilis and Pseudomonas aeruginosa suggesting its broad spectrum antimicrobial activity.

4. Antioxidant activity

Haritaki shows In vitro evaluation of tri-ethyl chebula is a strong antioxidant and freeradical scavenger, which is help for anti-oxidative ability.

2] Neem

Fig 2: Neem

Common name: Neem.

Synonym: Indian lilac.

Scientific name: Azadirachta indica.

Family: Meliaceae.

Biological source: fresh or dried leaves and seed oil of Azadirachta indica

J. Juss (Melia Indica or M. azadirachta Linn.).

Chemical constituents: nimbolinin, nimbin, nimbidin, nimbidol, sodium nimbinat.

Applications: Antifungal, Anti-bacterial, Anti-inflammatory.

Taxonomical Classification:

Kingdom	Plantae
Division	Magnoliophyta
Order	Sapindales
Family	Meliaceae
Genus	Azadirachta
Species	A. indica

Fig 3: Turmeric**Pharmacological Properties:****1. Anti-bacterial**

An experiment was made to evaluate the antibacterial activity of the bark, leaf, seed, and fruit extracts of *Azadirachta indica* on bacteria isolated from adult mouth and results revealed that bark and leaf extracts showed antibacterial activity against all the test bacteria used.

2. Anti-inflammatory activity

Results of a study revealed that neem leaf extract showed significant anti-inflammatory effect. Results of a study revealed that neem leaf extract showed significant anti-inflammatory effect. study results suggest that nimbidin suppresses the functions of macrophages and ulcer, and rheumatism. To control different skin infections neem, oil has been found to be useful.

3. Anti-fungal activity

A study showed the antimicrobial role of aqueous extracts of neem cake in the inhibition of spore germination against three sporulating fungi such as *C. lunata*, *H. penniseti*, and *C. gloeosporioides* f. sp. *Mangiferae* and results of the study revealed that methanol and ethanol extract of *Azadirachta indica* showed growth inhibition against *Aspergillus flavus*, *Alternaria solani*, and *Cladosporium*.

3] Turmeric

Common name: Turmeric.

Synonym: Saffron Indian, Curcuma, Curcumin.

Scientific name: *Curcuma longa*, *Curcuma aromatica*.

Family: Zingiberaceae.

Biological source: Rhizomatous herbaceous perennial plant belonging to the ginger family Zingiberaceae.

Chemical constituents: curcumin (CUR), demethoxy curcumin (DMC) and bisdemethoxycurcumin (BDMC).

Applications: anti-inflammatory, anti-HIV, anti-bacterial, antioxidant, nematocidal, antiparasitic, antispasmodic.

Taxonomical Classification:

Kingdom	Plantae
Division	Magnoliophyta
Class	Liliopsida
Subclass	Zingiberidae
Order	Zingiberales
Family	Zingiberaceae
Genus	Curcuma
Species	<i>C. longa</i>

Pharmacological Properties:**1. Anti-inflammatory properties**

Oral administration of curcumin in instances of acute inflammation was found to be as effective as cortisone or phenylbutazone. Oral administration of *Curcuma longa* significantly reduced inflammatory swelling. *C. longa*'s anti-inflammatory properties may be attributed to its ability to inhibit both biosynthesis of inflammatory

prostaglandins from arachidonic acid, and neutrophil function during inflammatory states.

2. Antioxidant properties

Water and fat-soluble extracts of turmeric and its curcumin component exhibit strong antioxidant activity, comparable to vitamins C and E. Clinical research on curcumin's therapeutic benefit for pancreatitis is limited and has primarily focused on its antioxidant properties.

3. Anticarcinogenic properties

The effect of *Curcuma longa* on myocardial apoptosis in experimentally induced myocardial ischemic-reperfusion injury was investigated by Mohanty et al. 2006. *Curcuma longa* demonstrated significant anti-apoptotic property, which might contribute to the observed preservation in cardioprotective properties and cardiac function.

4. Antimicrobial properties

Turmeric extract and the essential oil of *Curcuma longa* inhibit the growth of a variety of bacteria, parasites, and pathogenic fungi. A study of chicks infected with the caecal parasite *Eimera maxima* demonstrated that diets supplemented with turmeric resulted in a reduction in small intestinal lesion scores and improved weight gain.

4] Aloe Vera

Fig 4: Aloe Vera

Common name: Aloe Vera.

Synonym: *Aloe barbadensis* Mill, *Aloe indica* Royle.

Scientific name: *Aloe barbadensis* Miller.

Family: *Asphodelaceae*.

Biological source: Dried latex of leaves of aloe vera.

Chemical constituents: Lupeol, salicylic acid, urea nitrogen, cinnamonic acid, phenols and sulfur.

Applications: Anti-oxidant, Anti-bacterial, Anti-inflammatory.

Taxonomical Classification:

Kingdom	Plantae
Phylum	Tracheophyta
Class	Liliopsida
Order	Asparagales
Family	Xanthorrhoeaceae
Genus	Aloe
Species	Aloe vera (L) Burm.f

Pharmacological Properties:

1. Anti-inflammatory action

Inflammation is an innate response of the body against an injury, characterized by swelling, pain, redness and heat, resulting in delay in the healing process. The anti-inflammatory action of Aloe vera gel not only relieves from pain and discomfort, but also accelerates the healing process.

2. Anti-oxidant effects

Aloe vera possesses enormous antioxidant effect. Glutathione peroxidase activity, superoxide dismutase enzymes and a phenolic anti-oxidant were found to be present in *A. vera*.

Materials and Methods

Collection:

First, we identified and collect the plant seeds of harad, aloe vera, neem and turmeric from the different localities of vathar and its nearby areas and washed them thoroughly with distilled water. The cleaned plant parts are then allowed for the complete shade drying and then made to a fine powder with a mechanical grinder and stored in an air-tight container.

Extraction:

1. Preparation of *Azadirachta Indica* (Neem) extract:

After gathering and properly cleaning the leaves with distilled water, the leaves were allowed to dry in the shade for a period of ten days. Powdered dried leaf material was created. After mixing 150 ml of 90% ethanol into 100 g of powder, it was placed in a percolator and allowed to macerate for seven days, stirring periodically, after being infused with 350 ml of 90% ethanol for three hours. A residue that was blackish-green was obtained by collecting and condensing the ethanolic extract. Airtight containers were used to store the extract in a dark, cold environment.

2. Preparation of Aloe vera:

Raw aloe vera is washed and green portion is completely removed. The transparent sticky mucilage is grinded and used as herbal extract of Aloe vera.

3. Preparation of harad:

Properly clean the seeds of harad with distilled water. Powdered dried seed material was created. After mixing 150 ml of 90% ethanol into 100 g of powder, it was placed in a percolator and allowed to macerate for seven days, stirring periodically, after being infused with 350 ml of 90% ethanol for three hours. A residue that was blackish-brown was obtained by collecting and condensing the ethanolic extract. Airtight containers were used to store the extract in a dark, cold environment.

Fig 5: Soxhlet apparatus

1. Preparation of turmeric:

After gathering and properly cleaning the rhizomes of curcuma longa with distilled water, the rhizomes were allowed to dry in the shade for a period of ten days. Powdered dried rhizomes material was created. After mixing 150 ml of 90% ethanol into 100 g of powder, it was placed in a percolator and allowed to macerate for seven days, stirring periodically, after being infused with 350 ml of 90% ethanol for three hours. A residue that was yellow was obtained by collecting and condensing the ethanolic extract. Airtight containers were used to store the extract in a dark, cold environment.

Screening

Preliminary phytochemical screening of harad:

Table 1: Preliminary phytochemical screening of harad

Test		Procedure	Observation	Inference
Alkaloids	1] Dragendorff's test	Dissolve a few mg of hydro-alcoholic until an acid reaction occurs, then add 1 ml of Dragendorff's reagent.	orange or orange-red precipitate is produced.	
	2] Hager's test	1 ml of Hydroalco-holic extract of the drug was taken in a test tube, adding a few drops of Hager's reagent.	yellow precipitate produced.	presence of alkaloids.
	3] Wagner's test	Acidifying 1 ml of hydro-alcoholic extract of the drug with 1.5% w/v of hydrochloric acid and adding	yellow or brown precipitate is formed.	

		a few drops of Wagner's reagent.		
Carbohydrates	1] Anthrone test	Take 2 ml of Anthrone test solution, adding 0.5 ml of hydro-alcoholic extract of the drug.	green or blue colour indicates.	presence of carbohydrates.
	3] Fehling's test	Take 2 ml of hydro-alcoholic extract of the drug adding 1 ml of a mixture of equal parts of Fehling's solution 'A' and Fehling's solution 'B' and boiling the contents of the test tube for few minutes.	red or brick red precipitate is formed.	
Flavonoids	1] Shinoda's test	In a test tube containing 0.5 ml of hydro-alcoholic extract of the drug, adding 5-10 drops of dil. hydrochloric acid followed by a small piece of magnesium.	pink, reddish pink or brown colour is produced.	Presence of flavonoids
Proteins	1] Millon's test	Dissolving a small quantity of hydroalcoholic of the drug in 1 ml of distilled water and adding 5-6 drops of Millon's reagent.	white precipitate is formed which turns red on heating.	
Steroids	1] Salkowski Reaction	Adding 1 ml of conc. sulphuric acid to 2 ml of hydro-alcoholic of the drug carefully, from the side of the test tube.	red colour is produced in the chloroform layer.	
Tannins		To 1-2 ml of plant hydro-alcoholic extract, adding a few drops of 5% FeCl ₃ solution was added.	green colour indicates	

Preliminary phytochemical screening of Turmeric:

Table 2: Preliminary phytochemical screening of Turmeric

Test		Procedure	Observation	Inference
Alkaloids	1] Dragendroff's test	Two drops of Dragendroff's reagent were added to 1ml of the filtrate.	A creamy precipitate was observed.	presence of alkaloids.
	2] Wagner's test	1ml of the filtrate was mixed with Wagner's reagent.	Brownish precipitate was formed.	presence of alkaloids.
Saponin		5ml of the ethanolic plant extract was	Frothing was observed.	presence of saponin.
		mixed with 20ml of sterile distilled water and then vigorously agitated in a test-tube (boiling-tube) and left to stand.		
Tannin		3ml of the plant extract was mixed with equal proportion of freshly prepared FeCl ₃ .	green colouration appeared.	presence of tannin.

Flavonoid		The Turmeric ethanolic extract was treated with 0.25M (10%) NaOH Solution.	bright yellow colour indicates.	presence of flavonoids.
Terpenoids		This test was carried out using the Salkowski's test. 5ml of the extract was mixed with 2ml of chloroform in a test-tube and 3ml of concentrated H ₂ SO ₄ acid was carefully added through the walls of the test-tube.	reddish-brown colour was observed.	presence of terpenoids.

Preliminary phytochemical screening of Neem:

Table 3: Preliminary phytochemical screening of Neem

Test		Procedure	Observation	Inference
Alkaloid	1] Dragendorff test	A few drops of Dragendorff reagent were added to 2.0ml of the extract and a solution of potassium bismuth iodine was also added.	orange colouration.	Presence of alkaloid.
	2] Wagner test	A few drops of the Wagner Reagent were added to 2.0ml of the extract and a solution of iodine in potassium iodine was also added.	deep brown precipitate would indicate.	presence of alkaloid.
Flavonoids		A few drops 10% of lead acetate solution was added to 2.0ml of the extract in a test tube.	cream or light yellow colourations.	presence of flavonoids.
Phenols		Two millilitres of the extract was added to 2ml of ferric chloride.	deep blush green solution indicates.	presence of phenols.
Resins		Two milliliters of acetic anhydride was added to 2.0ml of the extract and a drop of concentrated sulphuric acid was also added.	purple colour, rapidly changing to violet indicates.	presence of resins.
Terpenes and Steroids		One millilitre of acetic anhydride was added to 2.0ml of the extract and then concentrated sulphuric acid was carefully added down the side of the test tube.	reddish brown colour at the interphase indicates.	presence of terpenes and steroids.

Preliminary phytochemical screening of Aloe Vera: ^[9-14]

Table 4: Preliminary phytochemical screening of Aloe Vera

Test	Procedure	Observation	Inference
Alkaloids	3ml of 1% hydrochloric acid was added to 3ml of methanolic extract on a steam bath. Wagner's and Mayer's reagents were added.	precipitates formation.	alkaloids presence.
Carbohydrates	2ml of Molisch reagent was added to 3 ml of methanolic extract. The mixture was well shaken. 2ml concentrated sulphuric acid was added carefully to the test tube.	purple ring at the junction indicated.	carbohydrates presence.

Glycosides	2ml of chloroform and 2ml of acetic acid were added to 2ml of extract carefully.	change in color from purple to blue to green indicated.	
Tannin	2ml of methanolic extract and 2ml of distilled water were mixed and few drops of ferric chloride solution (5% w/v) were added.	green precipitates formed.	presence of tannins.
Saponins	5ml of methanol extract and 5ml of distilled water were shaken robustly and heated in a test tube.	Stable foam was formed.	presence of saponins.
Flavonoids	1ml methanol extract was added to 1ml lead acetate (10%) solution.	yellow precipitates formed.	presence of flavonoids.
Terpenoids	2ml of chloroform was mixed with 2ml of extract and evaporated to dryness. 2ml of concentrated sulphuric acid) was added and heated for 2 minutes.	grey coloration confirmed.	presence of terpenoids.

Formulation

Table 5: Ingredients

Sr. No.	Ingredients
1.	Bees wax
2.	Mineral oil
3.	Borax
4.	Water
5.	Methyl paraben
6.	Orange Peel oil
7.	Harad
8.	Neem
9.	Aloe Vera
10.	Turmeric

- Melt the bees wax and mineral oil (almond oil) together and bring to a temp to 70°C.
- Dissolve borax and methyl paraben in water and bring the temp of this solution to 70°C.
- Add water phase to oil phase with rapid stirring.
- After the addition of water, agitated slowly while cooling.

- Add the extracts, perfume and preservative at the temp at 50°C.
- Fill into the jars when cream has cooled to 42°C.

Fig 6: Formulation Batches of cream formulation

Table 6: Batches of cream formulation

S. No.	Ingredients (Plant Extract)	Formulation F1H	Formulation F2H	Formulation F3H
1.	Harad	0.5 ml	0.2 ml	0.4 ml
2.	Neem	0.5 ml	0.2 ml	0.4 ml
3.	Turmeric	0.5 ml	0.2 ml	0.4 ml
4.	Aloe Vera	1.5 ml	1 ml	1 ml

Table 7: Batches of cream formulation

S. No.	Excipients	Formulation	Formulation	Formulation
		F1H	F2H	F3H
1.	Bees wax	3 g	3.5 g	3.2 g
2.	Mineral oil	10 ml	10.5 ml	10.2 ml
3.	Borax	0.2 g	0.4 g	0.3 g
4.	Water	Q. S	Q. S	Q. S
5.	Methyl paraben	0.02 g	0.04 g	0.03 g
6.	Orange peel oil	Q. S	Q. S	Q. S

Evaluation of cream

1. Physical evaluation:

Formulated herbal cream was further evaluated by using the following physical parameters. Colour, Odour, Consistency, and state of the formulation.

(a) Colour:

The colour of the cream was observed by visual examination. The result is slightly yellow.

(b) Odour:

The odour of cream was found to be characteristics.

(c) Consistency:

The formulation was examined by rubbing cream on hand manually. The cream having smooth consistency. Cream did not leave greasy substances on skin surface after application.

(d) State:

The state of cream was examined visually. The cream having a semisolid state.

2. Washability:

Formulation was applied on the skin and then ease extends of washing with water was checked. Result is easily washable.

3. Non-irritancy test:

Herbal cream formulation was evaluated for the non-irritancy test. Observation of the sites was done for 24 hrs. Result is non-irritant.

4. Viscosity:

Viscosity of cream was done by using Brooke field viscometer at the temp of 25 °C using spindle no.63 at 5rpm. Result is 39010cps.

5. Phase separation:

The prepared cream was transferred in a suitable wide mouth container. Set aside for storage, the oil phase and aqueous phase separation were visualizing after 24hrs. Result is no phase separation.

6. Spread ability:

The spread ability was expressed in terms of time in seconds taken by two slides to slip off from the cream, placed in between the slides, under certain load. Lesser the time taken for separation of the two slides better the spread ability. Two sets of glass slides of standard dimension were taken. Then one slide of suitable dimension was taken and the cream formulation was placed on that slide. Then other slide was placed on the top of the formulation. Then a weight or certain load was placed on the upper slide so that the cream between the two slides was pressed uniformly to form a thin layer. Then the weight was removed and excess of formulation adhering to the slides was scrapped off. The upper slide was allowed to slip off freely by the force of weight tied to it. The time taken by the upper slide to slip off was 10 sec. Result is 22.8 (g×cm/sec).

$$\text{Spread ability} = m \times l/t$$

Where,

m= Standard weight which is tied to or placed over the upper slide (30g)

l= length of a glass slide (5 cm)

t= time taken in seconds.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

All the parameters which were evaluated found to give good results and the results are tabulated below.

Table 8: Observation

Sr.no.	Parameter	Observation
1.	Colour	slightly yellow
2.	Odor	characteristics
3.	Consistency	smooth
4.	State	semisolid
5.	Washability	easily washable
6.	Non-irritancy test	Non-irritant
7.	Viscosity	39010cps
8.	Phase separation	No phase separation
1.	Spread ability	22.8 (g×cm/sec)

The herbal cream are the preparation which are used for the treatment of acne vulgaris. The herbal cream are widely used due to their no or less side effects as compared to conventional cream, because it contains pure natural or herbal ingredients rather than synthetic chemicals. Herbal cream does not require animal testing and it is earth and skin friendly.

CONCLUSION

Water in oil emulsion-based cream was formulated using natural ingredients and was evaluated. By combining all these ingredients, it can be concluded that this cream can be used as a anti-acne cream and the ingredients mixed can produce synergistic effect of the other. Further studies can be carried out on stability and skin irritancy test of the cream.

REFERENCE

- Adégbidi H, Koudoukpo C, Atadokpèdé F, do Ango-Padonou F, Yédomon HG. Epidemiological and clinical aspects of acne in the dermatology Department of the Teaching Hospital of Parakou (Benin). *Journal of Cosmetics, Dermatological Sciences and Applications*. 2014 Apr 29;2014.
- Haris HH, Ming KY, Moon KT, Kim NS, Bum LC, Kotak V. Evaluation of efficacy and safety of Avoc acne gel for acne: an open, single centric, non-comparative study for 8 weeks. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res*. 2012;5(3):73-6.
- Burns T, Breathnach SM, Cox N, Griffiths C, editors. *Rook's textbook of dermatology*. John Wiley & Sons; 2008 Apr 15.
- Till AE, Goulden V, Cunliffe WJ, Holland KT. The cutaneous microflora of adolescent, persistent and late-onset acne patients does not differ. *British journal of dermatology*. 2000 May 1;142(5):885-92.
- James KA, Burkhart CN, Morrell DS. Emerging drugs for acne. *Expert opinion on emerging drugs*. 2009 Dec 1;14(4):649-59.
- Burkhart CN, Burkhart CG. Microbiology's principle of biofilms as a major factor in the pathogenesis of acne vulgaris. *International journal of dermatology*. 2003 Dec;42(12):925-7.
- Bag A, Bhattacharyya SK, Chattopadhyay RR. The development of *Terminalia chebula* Retz. (Combretaceae) in clinical research.

- Asian Pacific journal of tropical biomedicine. 2013 Mar 1;3(3):244-52.
8. Arora S, Kaur K, Kaur S. Indian medicinal plants as a reservoir of protective phytochemicals. Teratogenesis, carcinogenesis, and mutagenesis. 2003;23(S1):295-300.
 9. Bista R, Ghimire A, Subedi S. Phytochemicals and antioxidant activities of Aloe Vera (*Aloe barbadensis*). *J Nut Sci Heal Diet*. 2020 Jun;1(1):25-36.
 10. Mazid M, Khan TA, Mohammad F. Role of secondary metabolites in defense mechanisms of plants.
 11. Samy RP, Ignacimuthu S, Raja DP. Preliminary screening of ethnomedicinal plants from India. *Journal of ethnopharmacology*. 1999 Aug 1;66(2):235-40.
 12. Parekh J, Karathia N, Chanda S. Evaluation of antibacterial activity and phytochemical analysis of *Bauhinia variegata* L. bark. *African Journal of Biomedical Research*. 2006;9(1).
 13. Harborne AJ. *Phytochemical methods a guide to modern techniques of plant analysis*. springer science & business media; 1998 Apr 30.
 14. Sofowora A. Research on medicinal plants and traditional medicine in Africa. *The Journal of Alternative and Complementary Medicine*. 1996 Sep 1;2(3):365-72.

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